

**A STUDY ON TOTAL EMPLOYEE INVOLVEMENT
ACTIVITIES IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN HOTEL,
PERAMBALUR**

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Abstract:

This project report titled as "A study on total employee involvement activities in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College" is a real time project human resource development for maintaining the morale of the employee. Through this study the researcher fined the effectiveness of existing total employee involvement activities for the employee who all is working in the organization. For the analytical study I took 52 samples from a total of 52 employees, in a complex random way. For this purpose I made a questionnaire with 24 questions, and collected the response. I used the statistical tool for the analysis work of these samples. The tools I used Chi-square test, Karl Person's Correlation and Percentage analysis.

Key Words: 52 Employees Questionnaire, Chi-Square Test, Karl Person's Correlation, Percentage Analysis

Introduction:

According to Stephen. P. Robins, employee involvement is, "a participative process that uses the entire capacity of employees and is designed to encourage increased commitment to the organization success." Assuring employee involvement in all activities is one of the important functions of the human resource department. The requirement needed for proper functionality of the company is identified to analyze the employees skill set to improve their efficiency and needs. In an increasingly competitive world economy, more and more organization treats employees as a major asset for competitive advantage by adopting the practices of employee involvement. The primary focus of Employee Involvement activities is to improve business through typing employee interest to business to business outcomes. Employee Involvement is not a unitary concept; rather, it incorporates a variety of technology that can refer to as different types of Employee Involvement programs.

The existing employee recognition policy has an objective to encourage active involvement on employee in their area of work by suggesting and implementing innovating and improvement to the processes, methodologies and systems resulting direct benefit to the company through Suggestion, Awards, Update, Awards, Quality Circle Awards and Annual of excellence.

Training program is conducted to ensure the individual possess the requisite skill to perform the current effectively and to prepare the workforce for future core competencies. Measuring the effectiveness of the Total Employee Involvement practices were the objective of this project using Chi-square and percentage Analysis. This will help the company to implement more Total Employee Involvement practices if the existing Total Employee Involvement practices are effective otherwise they can modify it. Better Total Employee Involvement make employee more efficient and there is a good relationship is built between the management and employee.

Review Literature:

"The human resource management function includes variety of activities and key among them is deciding what staffing needs you have and whether to use independent contractors or hire employees to fill these needs, recruiting and training the best employees, ensuring they are high performance, dealing with performance issues, and ensuring your personnel and management practices conform to various regulations. Activities also include managing you approach to employee benefits and motivation. One of such type of activity is Total employee Involvement". "Suggestion scheme is an innovative way of sparking the creativity of the workforce, and providing a proven system of capturing hundreds of ideas in a short period of time". The goal is to get least one idea per week from everyone in the organization during the time period. All ideas are evaluated and each participant receives recognition for their contributions. There are many models of how Employee Involvement operates also have been developed. The models are;

Lowen (1968) defined participative decision making as situation "in which decisions as to activities are arrived at by the personal who are to execute those decisions". He went to emphasize on what factors should lead to successful Employee Involvement. In his model the effectiveness of involvement depends on the personality and attitude of those involved; the extend, importance and visibility of those issues addressed; and the quality of the participation process (e.g. Clarity of goals, amount of useful information available exclusively to the subordinate, and extent to which subordinates can exert control over productivity).

Limitations of the Study:

- The sample size is restricted for the research purpose; there for the results obtained will be only of appropriate in nature.
- It was difficult to contact the employees, as many of them busy with their regular day to day activities.
- During the interview schedule it was difficult to translate the various concepts to the worker level in language.
- The research was mistaken by few of the workers as a management representative one and they were hesitant to answer truly, and even accepting the questionnaire when approached.

Objective of the Study:

- To find the various factors that influenced in employee involvement.
- To analyze the factor this makes hindrance towards employee involvement
- To suggest the measure to be taken to develop employee involvement activities

Methodology:

A research method is a systematic plan for conducting research. Sociologists draw on a variety of both qualitative and quantitative research methods, including experiments, survey research, participant observation, and secondary data. Quantitative methods aim to classify features, count them, and create statistical models to test hypotheses and explain observations. Qualitative methods aim for a complete, detailed description of observations, including the context of events and circumstances.

Hypothesis:

- H0: There is no significance relationship between the two variables.
- H1: There is significance relationship between the two variables.

Karl Pearson’s Co-Efficient of Correlation:

- It is used to measure the degree of relationship between two variables. The co- efficient assumes
- That there is linear relationship between two variables.
- That the two variables are casually related which means that one of the variables is dependent and other is independent.

$$\text{Correlation co-efficient}(r) = \frac{\sum dx dy}{\sqrt{\sum dx^2} \sqrt{\sum dy^2}}$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} dx &= X - \text{mean of } X \\ dy &= Y - \text{mean of } Y \\ r &= \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{(n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2)} \sqrt{(n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2)}} \end{aligned}$$

Research Design:

The researcher used Descriptive Research Design. Descriptive Research design means fact finding one. The Research used this research design to find out the fact of respondents attitude and opinion about student empowerment.

Sampling Design:

The Sampling type is Simple Random Sample which involves deliberating selection of particular units constituting a sample, which represents the universe, is used for conducting the study.

Sample Size:

Sample size denotes the number of sample selected for the study. They sample size for this study is fixed at 52 respondents.

Data Collection Method:

Data are the basic input to any decision making processing of data gives statistics of importance of study.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data

Primary Data:

Primary Data were collected through Questionnaire. The data which are collected a fresh for the first time and happen to be original in character.

Statistical Tools and Techniques:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-square test
- Correlation

Percentage Analysis:

In this analysis the various kinds of research are submitted separately and the percentage of response by the respondents in that category is find out by dividing

$$= \frac{\text{Percentage of the respondents}}{\text{Frequency of responses} \times 100 \text{ Total of respondents}}$$

Chi-Square:

Like t and f test a chi-square distribution is also function of its degree of freedom. This distribution is skewed to the right and the random variables can never take a negative value. Theoretically, its range is from zero to infinity

$$\text{Chi-Square}(x^2) = \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

Here,

E_i = Expected frequency,

O_i = Observed frequency

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Age Wise Classification Table:

S.No	Particular	Frequency	Percentage
1	Below 25	11	22
2	B/W 25-50	33	62
3	Above 50	8	16
	Total	52	100

Chart:

Age Wise Classification:

Inference:

From the table and chart it is found that 62% of respondents are between 33 years age.

Correlation:

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
25	30	625	900	750
24	17	576	289	408
3	5	9	25	15
52	52	1210	1214	1173

$$\sum X=52, \sum Y=52, \sum X^2=1210, \sum Y^2=1214, \sum XY=1173$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2} \sqrt{n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2}} = 0.876$$

Inference:

There is high Positive Correlation between Current Continuous Assessment Practices (X) and one of the Best Continuous Assessment Practices (Y).

Findings:

- Majority of employees are 25-50 years old. Education qualification of 48% employees are under graduates and 19% of employees are 10th and 5% of employees are 12th and 3% of employees are post graduates.
- Around 65% of respondents satisfied with existing suggestion scheme and 35% of respondents neutral with suggestion scheme. From this we can understand that almost all respondents are satisfied with existing suggestion scheme.
- Around 2% of respondents not facing any difficulties while giving a suggestion and 58% of respondents agreed that suggestion scheme increases their participation in Total Employee Involvement activities.

- Around 67% of respondents agreed that existing suggestion scheme awards encourages them to give more suggestions. Around 58% of respondents satisfied with existing kitchen and they agreed that it improves their working environment.
- 63% of respondents agreed that they are getting good support from their colleagues to implement a update successfully and 52% of respondents agreed that training given enough knowledge to participate activity in update.
- Around 58% of respondent level of satisfaction in quality circle activity and 63% of respondents satisfied with the duration for the completion of a quality circle activity.
- Among the respondents around 48% of respondents satisfied with existing training programs under Total Employee Involvement Activities
- Around 58% of respondents agreed that they are facing difficulties during training period and 56% of respondents agreed that they are getting communications regarding Total Employee Involvement at right time.
- Around 54% of respondents agreed that existing Total Employee Involvement activities improves their relationship with management and 54% of respondents agreed that it improves morale of the employees also.
- Around 44% of respondents are neutral with the flexibility in the organization and 42% of respondents are satisfied with the personnel policies in the organization.

Suggestions:

Suggestion schemes should be encouraged so as to get more employees involved. Around half of the respondents suggested that training will give enough knowledge to participate actively in TEI activities so organization should give more training regarding kaizen under TEI. It will increase employee participation and active involvement. Majority of respondents are not satisfied with existing quality circle activities main reasons are dissatisfaction in existing circle and duration giving for the completion of a quality circle activity. They are expecting external participation or presentation as awards for their best performance in QC. Organization can arrange such programs and give them a chance to present their best performance

Inter departmental coordination should be improved so as to provide a good working conditions which will help the employee to be more involved. Majority of respondents are dissatisfied with existing programs under TEI. More than half of the respondents faced difficulties at the time of training like lack of time, lack of confidence to implement new ideas, lack of coordination etc, if we can avoid these, we can assure 100% satisfaction in training. The company should motivate the employees for their performance by increasing their salary rates and also by given certain rewards for their services.

Conclusion:

Based on the present study on total employee involvement activities with respect to Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Hotel, I came to the following conclusion that the employees are not satisfied with the Quality circle reward system, being followed by the company, for their best performance in total employee involvement activities they said that it has to be changed and they have to be rewarded with cash prize and certificate to make them active in total employee involvement activities. Employee involvement is one of the most important factors of help the employees in motivating them and also by providing a good working environment, to help them to do quality work in the organization.

Rewards and kaizen have more influence for the improvement of total employee involvement in the organization. Existing total employee involvement activity increase the morale of the employee and it improves the relationship with management and employees. In general I conclude that TEI activities with respect to Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Hotel are effective in present situation.

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